

A Conceptual Model for the Prediction of Coronavirus (Covid-19) Spread in Nigeria

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Abstract - The novel coronavirus (Covid-19) was first reported in Wuhan in the Hubei province of China in late December, 2019. The outbreak of the disease has ravaged more than 200 countries and regions of the world which necessitated the World Health Organization (WHO) to declare it as a pandemic and a health challenge in the 21st century of international concern. The rate of its spread and severity has been an issue of concern especially in developing countries that have weak health system. With the radical increase in the number of confirmed cases and recorded deaths globally due to Covid -19 infections, it is crucial to predict the rate of the disease spread for sustainable interventions from relevant and donor agencies using infectious disease modeling tool. A modified Susceptibility-Exposure-Infection-Recovery (SEIR) has been adopted to analyse and predict the spread of the infections in Nigeria for the period of May 1, 2020 to June 9, 2020 using the life updates data of confirmed cases available on the website of Nigeria Centre for Disease Control. R studio software was used for the implementation of the model and prediction. The result of the prediction shows an accuracy of 72 per cent.

Keywords: infectious disease modelling, prediction model, covid-19, likelihood, Susceptible Exposed Infectious Recovered

I. INTRODUCTION

The emerging and reemerging diseases have led to a revived interest in developing models for the spread of infectious diseases. Since the first confirmed and reported case of Covid-19 (Coronavirus Disease 2019) in late 2019 in the city of Wuhan, China, the spread of the disease has cut across more than 200 countries and territories of the world. However, the pattern of transmission varies from region to region. The worldwide spread of the disease has necessitated its pronouncement as a pandemic by the World Health Organization on 11 March 2020. It has been established that through respiratory droplets, there is human-to-human transmission of this disease. [1]. Infectious diseases modeling provides useful

information to understand the diseases spread in host populations in a given time and space [2].

The first confirmed Covid-19 case was reported in Nigeria by Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) on February 27, 2020 and as at the time of writing this report, more than 19000 cases have been confirmed with over 5000 recovered cases and over 400 deaths have been recorded. [3] reported that the major spread of the disease is not unconnected with little awareness of the new virus, and surprisingly there are diverse opinions that either the cases are under reported or over reported, insufficient testing kits, poor or inconsistent results, and poor policy formulation and implementation for proper prevention and control measures to be adopted during the early stage of the outbreak. There are also cases of logistics challenges because of limited testing laboratories.

Covid 19 outbreak has been declared as a public health emergency that is of international concern to the World Health Organization [4].

Limited data and information on Covid-19 has hindered the prediction of its spread at the initial stage of the outbreak especially in regions that did not record confirmed cases at the initial stage of the outbreak. However, as cases keep rising steadily, more data and information become available for the prediction of its spread.

[5] noted that mathematical models could serve as a useful tool in understanding the associated risks with the spread of infectious diseases. For example, the models could predict the chance of infectious disease outbreak in a particular region, the likely number of cases in a given period of time and the expected interventions effects. The validity of the prediction results can yield to useful outputs if the model provides an accurate or near accurate representation of the reality.

The emergence and prevalence of any disease outbreaks depend on many factors such as economic activities, population mobility, and social environment [6].

[7] employ human migration data to model the transmission of Covid-19 based on intercity from the epicentre of the disease. The study forecast that Covid-19 spread will peak in February. This is contrary to the reality as the spread of the disease has doubled the figure after February 2020.

Most times, real life data is evidently scarce for early response to a disease outbreak because of a number of factors. Factors such as poor healthcare system, poor working conditions for the major stakeholders in the health sector and inadequate testing capacity facilitate the spread of the pandemic in Nigeria. The aim of this study is to predict the spread of Covid-19 in Nigeria based on the historical data of infected, recovered and death cases from the official website of Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC). The data was also used for model fitting. Many studies have been carried out on model predictions for the spread of infectious diseases during any outbreak however, if many independent research groups develop independent models that converge on a qualitatively similar output, confidence in model accuracy increases. Taking Nigeria as a case study, we predict the ongoing spread of the disease for a period of one month.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the related works. In section III, the methodology of the work is reported. Section IV reports the results of implementation and in section V, the summary of the study is given.

II. RELATED WORKS

[8] highlighted that prediction models help our understanding of the severity and spread of an infectious disease when we compare model results with observed variables. The model output can provide useful guidelines to decision makers for sustainable intervention deliverables against the disease dynamics.

[9] stated that early prediction of infectious disease outbreak provides a useful insight to effective monitoring, prevention and control for effective management of the situation. On-spatial and population-based data are used in traditional mathematical models to represent the dynamics of infectious diseases outbreak and view the disease spread assuming there is homogeneity in the transmission. The representations can be used to estimate the size of the population that can likely be affected by the infection, however, the models do not reveal the causal factors in the development of the diseases.

Tracking the spread and growth rate of pandemics helps provide early warning signals to both the populace and policy makers in which such information enables people to begin to change their style of living, and also enables government and health agencies to plan [10]. For states within the federation, it is imperative that the governments find means of continually monitoring the growth rate of Covid-19

virus across the nation and look for ways of curtailing the spread. Since February 27 when the first covid-19 index case was reported in Nigeria [11], Nigeria government has been fighting to keep the number of cases low. [12] worked on forecasting the spread of covid-19 in Nigeria using box-Jenkins modelling procedure. The study focused on the analysis of the spread of Covid-19 in Nigeria, applying statistical models and available data from the NCDC using a ten day forecast. [13] worked on covid-19 outbreak prediction with machine learning. The study presented a comparative analysis of machine learning and soft computing models to predict the Covid-19 outbreak as an alternative to (Susceptible-infected-recovered) SIR and SEIR models. [14] developed an online forecasting of Covid-19 cases in Nigeria using limited data. The model proposed an online forecasting mechanism that streamed data from the Nigeria Centre for Disease Control to update the parameters of an ensemble model which in turn provided updated Covid-19 forecasts in every 24 hours.

Advancements in computing technology and increased access to disease-related spatial data have made the modeling of the disease spread possible in space and time. [15] applied bond percolation on random graphs for the modeling of the spread of infectious disease through heterogeneous populations. Diverse mathematical techniques that provide understanding to the forecast and control of the spread of infectious diseases are growing rapidly.

[16] reported a time series forecasting model for short term prediction of the transmission of Covid-19 for early management of the outbreak. Many factors contribute to the fast spread of the disease. Inadequate data at the early stage of any infectious diseases outbreak makes it difficult to attain accurate simulation result however, estimation of preliminary parameters such as recorded fatalities and average latency through existing data can provide helpful information to minimise the infection rate.

Early understanding of the transmission dynamics of Covid-19 infection and effective evaluation of the control measures is presented in [17]. The early information assist in the assessment of the potential outbreaks and transmission in new regions. The study used periodic transmission estimation to assess the potential of human-to-human transmission in other regions other than the city of Wuhan where the first confirmed case of the disease was recorded.

[18] proposed a conceptual model for Covid-19 outbreak in Wuhan. Government actions such as travel restrictions and behavioural reaction of individuals were considered in the model. The study focused on the developments of the disease in Wuhan, China.

[19] presented a regional simulation and prediction of the spread of Corona virus in a selected region in Africa under three interventions which include suppression, mitigation, and mildness. [20-22] reported that epidemic transmission mechanism dynamic equations can be modeled mathematically

than statistical representations. These methods most times require sufficient data to run effectively, therefore these methods can be used at the early stages of epidemic transmission accurately predict the epidemic transmission indicators in a short term for the provision of short-term intervention and emergency prevention programs. [23] applied Baye's theorem and artificial neural network to build a predictive model. Comparative analysis was carried out on the performance level of the two methods. [24] adopted data mining techniques to predict possible students that are likely to graduate in terminal classes. However, the algorithm was implemented on a few dataset. The study therefore adopt a modified susceptibility exposure infection recovery model in predicting the spread of Covid-19 in Nigeria.

III. METHODOLOGY

In research community, the standard Susceptible Exposed Infectious Recovered (SEIR) model has been widely applied to model infectious diseases outbreaks. The study adopted an improved SEIR model [22].

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dS}{dt} = -\beta \frac{SI}{N} \alpha S \\ \frac{dE}{dt} = \beta \frac{SI}{N} - \gamma E \\ \frac{dI}{dt} = \gamma E - \delta I \\ \frac{dQ}{dt} = \delta I - \lambda Q - \kappa Q \\ \frac{dR}{dt} = \lambda Q \\ \frac{dD}{dt} = \kappa Q \\ \frac{dP}{dt} = \alpha S \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where S represents the number of susceptible population, E denotes the exposed cases, I represents the infected cases but not quarantined, Q denotes the confirmed cases and quarantined, R denotes the recovered cases, D is the recorded deaths, and P represented the unsusceptible population. $\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \delta, \lambda$ and κ denote the protection rate, infection rate, average incubation time, average quarantined time, treated/cure rate, and death rate. N represents the total population which is $N = S + E + I + R$.

The World Health Organization (WHO, 2020) estimated the death rate as 0.034 based on the past

incidents and the expected clinical reports. The formulation for the death parameter is given as:

$$\frac{dD}{dt} = 0.034 * I(t) \quad (2)$$

Delay difference in the parameters is used to construct the modified SEIR model based on the assumptions made above.

$$S(t + 1) = S(t) - \frac{\beta * E(t) * S(t)}{N} \quad (3)$$

$$E(t + 1) = E(t) + \frac{\beta * E(t) * S(t)}{N} - \alpha * E(t - 7) \quad (4)$$

$$I(t + 1) = I(t) + \alpha * E(t - 7) - \gamma * I(t) \quad (5)$$

$$R(t + 1) = R(t) + \gamma * I(t) \quad (6)$$

$$D(t + 1) = 0.034 * I(t) \quad (7)$$

The Nigeria Centre for Disease Control (NCDC) is the Nigerian Government health body that is saddled with the responsibilities of all interventions toward the prevention and control of infectious diseases. The data for the analysis and prediction of Covid 19 in Nigeria was collated from the live updates that are released in the website of the organisation <http://covid19.ncdc.gov.ng/>. In summarising the data, daily new cases confirmations and deaths were steadily increasing.

Though the first confirmed case was reported by NCDC on February 27, 2020 however, the collected data for analysis and prediction covers the period of May 1, 2020 to June 9, 2020.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

After formulating the model used in simulating the data set, the model was implemented using R studio software. Analysis and prediction of the data was carried out by the prediction toolbox package available in the R studio software. The package supports forecasting of time series data based on an additive model where non-linear trends are fit with yearly, weekly and daily seasonality. Figure 1 shows the relationship of Covid-19 confirmed cases in Nigeria between the periods of January 22nd, 2020 to June 9th, 2020. Figure 1 shows a drastic increase in the number of confirmed Covid-19 cases in Nigeria in the month of April with steady increase in subsequent months.

Fig. 1: Number of confirmed cases between February 2020 to June 2020

Fig. 2 shows the relationship between the numbers of Covid-19 confirmed cases in Nigeria against the predicted within the period in focus. The blue line

indicates predicted cases and the faint blue shade showing the prediction is still within the boundary of expected cases

Fig. 2: Number of confirmed cases vs predicted cases between February 2020 – June 2020

Figure 2 shows the relationship between the numbers of confirmed Covid-19 cases reported by NCDC against the predicted cases.

Fig. 3 shows the relationship between the number of confirmed Covid-19 cases and the predicted cases

against the days of the week for the period under review. It shows that low cases are recorded on Wednesdays and Thursdays. This does not mean that the virus is inactive on those days as there are many factors that can contribute to the low records such as

few people reporting for sample collection, logistics in transferring samples to the NCDC laboratory network and insufficient testing kits.

Fig. 3: Confirmed vs predicted cases against the days of the week.

Fig. 4 shows the line graph of the analysis of the predicted number of cases and the actual confirmed

cases. The red line shows the level of prediction accuracy.

Fig. 4: Plot diagram for predicted Number of confirmed cases as against the actual number of confirmed cases.

The Fig. 5 shows the percentage error of the prediction within the period of May 1 to June 9 2020 against the actual figure reported by NCDC.

Fig. 5: percentage error of the prediction

V. CONCLUSION

The proposed model was used in predicting the number of confirmed cases from May 1st to June 2020 with data gotten from the website of NCDC. The model was simulated using the prediction toolbox of R studio software and the results of the behaviour of the proposed model presented as plot diagrams. The model can be applied to other forecasting problems. It is believed that this model will inform NCDC of an idea of what number of confirmed cases is expected every day and further help in discovering ways of curtailing further spread of the virus. The projection will provide an insight into governmental intervention programmes and monitoring policies.

DISCLAIMER

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CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interests.

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